

Arctic and Antarctic Surface Temperatures from AVHRR thermal Infrared satellite sensors 1982–2023

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ABSTRACT

42-years of Arctic and Antarctic Surface Temperatures from thermal Infrared satellite radiometers (AASTI) are presented as the Copernicus Climate Change Service Ice surface temperature record v1.1 dataset (C3S IST). It covers snow, ice and ocean surfaces with mean and max–min daily temperatures poleward of 50 degrees North and South, for the period 1982–2023. The C3S IST is provided as a Level 3 (L3) dataset in a polar 0.25° latitude and longitude grid. It consists of two parts: (1) the C3S IST climate data record (ISTCDR v1.1), covering the period 1. January 1982 to 30. June 2019, and (2) the C3S IST Interim CDR version 1.1 (ICDR v1.1) covering 1. July 2019 to 31. December 2023. The surface temperatures (STs) are calculated from satellite thermal infrared Brightness Temperature (T_B) measurements from the Global Area Coverage – Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer (GAC - AVHRR) data, creating a comprehensive data set based solely on a single sensor type. The underlying AASTI algorithm is a combination of algorithms specifically tuned for sea ice, marginal ice zone, land ice and high latitude open water. In addition, each of the algorithm coefficients are tuned specifically for each of the AVHRR instruments, using simulated Top of the atmosphere (TOA) T_B s and ERA-Interim reanalysis surface and atmosphere data. Simulated TOA T_B 's are computed using the community radiative transfer model, RTTOV v12.3. Spatially and temporally varying uncertainties are computed for each data-point. The C3S IST surface temperatures were validated against different in situ observation types, where comparison against radiometric temperatures from flight campaigns and ice sheet station data resulted in smaller mean differences of 0.20°C and -1.84°C in the Northern Hemisphere (NH) than for validations against met station air temperatures, which were usually 1–3°C higher. Surface temperature climatology and trends have been computed for sea ice and ice sheets, showing large regional differences in surface temperature trends within the NH. For the entire dataset, the average trend is +1.11 °C/decade for the NH sea ice, +0.16 °C/decade for the Southern Hemisphere (SH) sea ice, +0.38 °C/decade for the Greenland ice sheet and -0.13 °C/decade for the Antarctic ice sheet. The positive trends are typically small during summer and larger during winter, e.g. in the Barents Sea, where trends exceed +0.3 °C/year in winter. Negative temperature trends are observed in some regions such as the Bering Strait's ice edge. For Antarctic sea ice, the trends are generally smaller and statistically less significant than those in the NH. The trends of the ice sheet surface show a similar pattern, where the Greenland Ice Sheet has positive trends, which both are largest and most significant in the coastal areas. The Antarctic Ice Sheet has diverse trends and large areas have statistically non-significant trends, except for the negative temperature trend in the central, high altitude part of east Antarctica exceeding -0.5 °C/year.

1. Introduction

The Surface Temperature (ST) is a function of the surface energy balance and at the same time affects the exchange of heat and gas

between the surface and the lower atmosphere. In Polar oceans, the growth and melting of sea ice, which drives critical (feedback) mechanisms in the polar environment and climate, such as albedo and lapse rate feedback and with implications for fresh water fluxes and

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Nomenclature**Acronyms**

T_B	Brightness Temperature
AASTI	Arctic and Antarctic Surface Temperatures from thermal Infrared satellite radiometers
ATBD	Algorithm theoretical basis document
AVHRR	Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer
AWS	Automatic Weather Station
C3S	Copernicus Climate Change Service
C3S IST	Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) ice surface temperature (IST) record v1.1 dataset
CASSTA	Composite Arctic Sea Surface Temperature Algorithm
CDR	Climate Data Record
CLARA	The CM SAF cLoud, Albedo and surface Radiation dataset from AVHRR data
CRREL	Cold Regions Research and Engineering Laboratory
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts
ECV	Essential Climate Variable
ERA	ECMWF Re-Analysis
EUMETSAT	European Organisation for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites
FCDR	Fundamental Climate Data Record
GAC	Global Area Coverage
GCOS	Global Climate Observing System
GDS	GHRSSST Data Specification
GHRSSST	Group for High Resolution Sea Surface Temperature
GISS	Goddard Institute for Space Studies
HadISST	The Met Office Hadley Centre's sea ice and sea surface temperature dataset
IABP	International Arctic Buoy Programme
ICDR	Interim Climate Data Record
ICDR v1.1	C3S IST Interim CDR version 1.1
L2	Level 2
L3	Level 3
LAC	Local Area Coverage
LST	Land Surface Temperature
MARS	Meteorological Archival and Retrieval System
MD	Mean Difference
MetOp	Meteorological Operational Satellite Program of Europe
MIZ	Marginal Ice Zone
MIZT	Marginal Ice Zone Surface Temperature
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NH	Northern Hemisphere

NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
NWP	Numerical Weather Prediction
OSISAF	Ocean and Sea Ice Satellite Application Facility
OSTIA	Operational Sea Surface Temperature and Ice Analysis
PROMICE	The Programme for Monitoring of the Greenland Ice Sheet
QL	Quality Levels
RTM	Radiative Transfer Model
RTTOV	Radiative Transfer for TOVS
SAF	Satellite Application Facility
SH	Southern Hemisphere
SIC	Sea Ice Concentration
SIMB3	Cryosphere Innovation Seasonal Ice Mass Balance Buoys 3
SST	Sea surface temperature
ST	Surface Temperature
STD	Standard deviation
sza	sun-zenith angle
TIR	Thermal Infrared
TIROS	Television Infrared Observation Satellite
TOA	Top of the atmosphere
TOVS	TIROS Operational Vertical Sounder

in Arctic surface temperatures are important indicators for global warming and Arctic amplification (Rantanen et al., 2022; Nielsen-Englyst et al., 2023). IST has also recently been selected as an Essential Climate Variable (ECV) by Global Climate Observing System (GCOS) (GCOS-244, 2022), indicating the need for long and stable IST CDRs. Long-term satellite data sets of ST offer consistency in polar areas where in situ observations are sparse.

To meet the needs for frequent and global coverage temperature information, several surface and air temperature data sets have been produced. The Global Ice and Sea Surface Temperature data set HadISST (Rayner et al., 2003), NOAA's Global integrated Land and Sea surface temperature Analysis (Vose et al., 2012) and the surface air temperature analysis from the Goddard Institute for Space Studies (GISS) (Hansen et al., 2010) are examples. However, these Surface Temperature data sets are based on data from different observational sources, such as irregularly sampled temperature observations from ships, observations from drifting buoys, air temperatures from automatic weather stations and skin temperature observations from satellite sensors. These observations are combined into daily analysis fields, despite varying quality and, at times, a large degree of incomparability that can reach several degrees Celsius (FRM4STS, 2018).

The Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) ice surface temperature (IST) record v1.1 dataset (C3S IST) presented here is based solely on thermal infrared satellite radiometer observations from 1982–2023, to ensure consistency in the input data and retrieval methodology, and to avoid biases from a model which is used for combining different data types in re-analysis data sets. Where satellite SST estimates usually match in situ measurements from e.g. drifting buoys with small standard deviations and low bias (Nielsen-Englyst et al., 2023; EUMETSAT, 2022), satellite IST and in situ comparisons are often associated with a larger Standard deviation (STD) and systematic bias. Measurement of surface temperature from buoys on sea ice is associated with a large uncertainty. However, the main error source for satellite IST is undetected and falsely categorized clouds. Undetected clouds contribute typically to larger STD and a cold bias in the satellite IST, because cloud tops

thermohaline circulation (IPCC, 2019; Pithan and Mauritsen, 2014; Taylor et al., 2018; Perovich and Polashenski, 2012) is a function of the sea and sea ice surface temperature (SST and IST) (Olonscheck et al., 2019). Surface Temperature is therefore an important input to numerical weather prediction and ocean-sea ice models, and trends

Table 1
Overview of the different datasets used during the processing of surface temperatures and validation.

Dataset	Description
Input data	
CLARA-A2.1/A3	The CM SAF Cloud, Albedo And Surface Radiation dataset from AVHRR data, version 2.1 and version 3
OSTIA	The Operational Sea Surface Temperature and Sea Ice Analysis (OSTIA) from the UK Met Office
NOAA NESDIS NGDC	NOAA elevation data to create land, sea and land-ice masks
OSISAF SIC	EUMETSAT & OSISAF sea ice concentration dataset (not actively used in the processing, but added to the C3S IST for postprocessing and filtering)
ERA-5 & ERA-Interim	Two reanalysis datasets by the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF)
In situ data for validation	
PROMICE AWS	Programme for Monitoring of the Greenland Ice Sheet (PROMICE) Automatic Weather Station's (AWS) (2008–2023)
NP drifting stations	Russian North Pole (NP) drifting ice stations (1982–1989 & 2003–2013)
ECMWF drifters	Drifting buoy data from the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) (1993–2015)
CRREL drifters	Drifting buoy data from the U.S. Army Cold Regions Research and Engineering Laboratory (CRREL) mass balance buoys (2001–2017)
SIMB3 drifters	Drifting buoy data from the Cryosphere Innovation Seasonal Ice Mass Balance Buoys 3 (SIMB3) (2019–2023)
IABP drifters	Buoy data from the International Arctic Buoy Programme (IABP) (1st of April 2017–1st of October 2021)
IceBridge data	Flight data from Operation IceBridge (IAKST1B) by NASA (2012–2019)

are usually colder than surface temperatures (Dybkjær et al., 2012). Clouds that are not detected by the cloud detection algorithm occur most frequently when it is dark and channels measuring in the reflected solar part of the spectrum have no data. Under these conditions the cloud detection algorithm relies only on infrared channels and NWP data (Eliasson et al., 2020; Dybbroe and amd K.-G. Karlsson, 2005b).

In general, very few observations of the temperature of the ice surface in situ are available to tune and validate the retrieval algorithms, especially over sea ice and in the Southern Hemisphere (SH). Instead, near-surface air temperatures (~1–2 m height) from buoys or weather stations are typically used. For that reason, both daytime and nighttime IST error statistics are overestimated due to differences between air and surface temperatures (Nielsen-Englyst et al., 2019; Høyer et al., 2018). Other significant contributions to estimated error statistics come from the data resampling procedures and are within the data sampling. In situ measurements from buoys or weather stations are point measurements with relatively high temporal frequency (6–24 times a day), while satellite measurements are areal average values with lower temporal frequency (1–8 times a day). Here, the Level 3 (L3) data of the C3S IST represents the average temperature on a 0.25 degree grid, which corresponds to an area of approximately $28 \times 28 \text{ km}^2$ at the equator. The time lag between two measurements can contribute to the mismatch between in situ and satellite measurements. This is, in particular, an issue during spring and autumn, where the diurnal variations can exceed $10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (Høyer et al., 2017).

The C3S IST consists of two parts. The first part is the C3S IST climate data record (ISTCDR v1.1), covering the period from 1982 to 30. June 2019, previously known as Arctic and Antarctic Surface Temperature from thermal Infrared (TIR) satellite sensors (AASTI v2.1), while the second part is the C3S IST Interim CDR (ICDR v1.1) covering the period from 1. July 2019 to 31. December 2023. C3S IST is based on data from the Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer (AVHRR 2&3) instruments on board US NOAA and European MetOp satellites. To our knowledge, it is the longest satellite ST record available based on a single sensor type. It covers Polar regions North of 50°N and South of 50°S for clear-sky conditions.

The objectives of this study are to describe the processing algorithms, the output data, and the validation. In addition, examples of data usage are provided here depicting temperature trends in the Arctic and Antarctic. The processing algorithm is tuned to multiple surface types, covering high-latitude water, sea ice, the marginal ice zone, and land ice. The calibration coefficients have been calculated for each individual AVHRR instrument by using reanalysis of the surface and atmosphere data to simulate Top of the atmosphere (TOA) T_B with the radiative transfer model RTTOV (v12.3) radiative transfer model (RTM).

The C3S IST differs from existing temperature records, as mentioned above, and focuses on three points, in particular: (1) the input to C3S IST is exclusively observations of surface Brightness Temperature

(T_B) from a single sensor-type; (2) Algorithms and data processing are consistent throughout the data set, and (3) The output surface temperature is derived directly from thermal surface radiation data, i.e., with no vertical temperature transformation involved. Compliance with all three points is crucial for the generation of consistent data sets for e.g. climate analysis, where temporal consistency and uncertainty estimations are very important.

The C3S IST data set has been validated with data from four long time series of in situ air temperature observations, and the results indicate a consistent data set with temperature trends that are largely much larger than the uncertainty of the data set (Dybkjær et al., 2024). Therefore, the data set offers a good basis for trend analysis of the last four decades' IST as well as input to other temperature analysis datasets, such as Nielsen-Englyst et al. (2023).

In this paper, the C3S IST data set is described in detail, i.e. the processing chain is presented and validation results, as well as climatological trends, are analyzed. The input data are described in Section 2, algorithms and output data sets in Section 3. Validation is presented in Section 4, while examples of the IST climatology and trends of IST are presented in Section 5. A discussion is presented in Section 6 and conclusions are given in Section 7.

2. Data

Several different data sources have been used to compute the C3S IST ST and related quantities, such as uncertainties. An algorithm calibration is applied before the surface temperatures are calculated. From the ERA-Interim reanalysis (Dee et al., 2011) surface temperatures, atmospheric temperature and humidity profile data are used for this algorithm calibration. Data are retrieved from the ECMWF MARS archive (ECMWF MARS Archive, 2021). The calibration is explained in detail in Section 3.2.

The data sources for the cloud masking, ST calculation, land–sea–ice areas, NWP parameters and in situ data used for the validation are listed in Table 1 and presented in the following paragraphs.

2.1. C3S IST input data

2.1.1. Radiance and cloud mask

The primary input data to the C3S IST algorithms are three thermal infrared radiance channels, retrieved by the AVHRR/2+3 radiometer instruments. The three channels on AVHRR/2+3 have center wavelengths at 3.7, 11 and $12 \mu\text{m}$, hereinafter are their measured brightness temperatures (T_B s) referred to as T_{B37} , T_{B11} and T_{B12} , respectively. In addition, the AVHRR channels measuring the shortwave part of the spectrum are inserted into the C3S IST processor and used for cloud detection during sunlit hours of the day (Dybbroe et al., 2005a; Dybbroe and amd K.-G. Karlsson, 2005b).

The TIR radiance data used in the C3S IST calculation and in the cloud screening procedure is not a CLARA-A2.1/A3 product parameter, but merely a part of the FCDR on which the CLARA-A2.1/A3 CDR is based (Karl-Göran et al., 2017, 2020; Karlsson et al., 2023). The CDR CLARA-A2 was used for 1982 to 2015 and extended with CLARA-A2.1 for 2016 to June 2019, while the ICDR CLARA-A3 was used from July 2019 onward. The radiance data used in the C3S IST data set are provided directly to the C3S IST development team by the CLARA development team from the Climate SAF (Climate SAF, 2021). In the current version of the C3S IST data set the radiances are not sensor intercalibrated. Instead, the temporal consistency of C3S IST is tested against long-term ground reference data sets (Dybkjaer et al., 2024). Furthermore, while the CLARA-A3 does introduce cloud probability values, these have not been included in the algorithm, to keep the processing consistent between CLARA versions.

The C3S IST input data are retrieved from the AVHRR/2+3 instruments on board NOAA 7, 9, 11, 12, 14, 15, 16 17, 18, 19 and MetOp A, B, and C, as level 1 b (L1b), full orbit swath data in Global Area Coverage mode (GAC). GAC is the reduced data format from the original Local Area Coverage mode (LAC). The value of the GAC pixel is the mean of 4 center along scan LAC pixel values. The GAC sampling procedure results in a spatial resolution of approximately 4 km at nadir. See, e.g. the AVHRR Level 1b Product Guide (EUMETSAT, 2011) for a more in-depth description of the GAC format.

The T_B data, cloud mask and satellite–sun–earth geometry data are generated by the Polar Platform System 2021 cloud processing software package, from the NoW Casting Satellite Application Facility (NWCSAF SMHI, 2021; Dybbroe et al., 2005a; Dybbroe and amd K.-G. Karlsson, 2005b).

The temporal coverage for each of the AVHRR instruments since 1979, including equator crossing time for each satellite, is illustrated in detail in Clerbaux et al. (2020). Data from NOAA 6, 8 and 10 are not applied in the C3S IST data record, because these satellites carry the AVHRR 1 instrument, which does not include the T_{B12} channel. T_{B12} is used by the SST and IST algorithms, jointly with T_{B11} (see the algorithm details in Section 3.1). The remaining satellites provide a continuous satellite record of global radiances since 1981.

2.1.2. Sea surface temperature climatology

Daily SST climatology from the OSTIA system (Donlon et al., 2012) provided by the UK Met Office (OSTIA, 2021) are used as a first guess for the daytime SST algorithm (see algorithm descriptions in Section 3.1).

2.1.3. Land, sea and land-ice masks

A mask with land, sea and Greenland and Antarctic ice-sheet classes is produced by combining the variables ‘ice_surface’ and ‘bedrock’ elevations from ETOPO1 data from NOAA NESDIS NGDC global relief maps (NOAA, 2014), as described in Dybkjaer et al. (2018a).

- Ice Sheet: if the ice_surface elevation minus the bedrock elevation is greater than 10 m.
- Ocean and Sea Ice: if the variable elevation ‘ice surface’ minus the elevation of the bedrock is less than or equal to -5 m.
- Land: Where none of the above applies.

2.1.4. Sea ice concentration

The EUMETSAT Ocean and Sea Ice Satellite Application Facility (OSISAF) Sea Ice Concentration (SIC) data (Tonboe et al., 2016; Lavergne et al., 2019) are added to the C3S IST data set. Data are collected from the OSISAF data archive (OSISAF, 2021). SIC data are not used by any algorithm, but merely passed to the output files for data filtering and postprocessing purposes.

2.1.5. NWP wind speed and air temperature

From the ERA-5 (Hans et al., 2020) and ERA-Interim reanalysis (Dee et al., 2011) wind speed and 2-m air temperatures are added to the C3S IST data set for data filtering and customization purposes. NWP data from the 4 daily analyses, at 00z, 06z, 12z and 18z are re-sampled to a 0.75 degree regular grid. The nearest NWP data point in time and space is passed on to C3S IST L2. The air temperature is also passed on the L3 product, as the mean of all valid L2 pixels within a given L3 grid.

2.2. Validation data

While the C3S IST dataset also contains SST values, the validation in this article will focus on the IST and ice Land Surface Temperature (LST). The following in situ data have been selected to test the C3S IST product:

For the validation of the land ice surface temperatures in the Northern Hemisphere, the Programme for Monitoring of the Greenland Ice Sheet (PROMICE) Automatic Weather Station’s (AWS) on the Greenland Ice Sheet (Ahlström et al., 2008; van As et al., 2011; Fausto et al., 2021) have been used. All land stations measure air temperatures at varying heights, partly due to varying snow accumulation, but typically around 2 m above the surface.

Drifting buoy data extracted from four different sources have been selected to create a long data record to validate IST in both hemispheres: For the early period 1982–1989, as well as 2003–2013 data from Russian North Pole (NP) drifting ice stations have been collected (RU/FSR/HME/AARI, NSIDC, 1993). Data for the period 1993–2015 distributed by the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) have been collected through the Meteorological Archival and Retrieval System (MARS). Another data collection covering the period 2001–2017 is provided by the US Army Cold Regions Research and Engineering Laboratory (CRREL) mass balance buoys (Perovich et al., 2016; Richter-Menge et al., 2006). The final buoy data comes from Cryosphere Innovation Seasonal Ice Mass Balance Buoys 3 (SIMB3) covering the period 2019–2023 (Cryosphere, 2011). All buoy data sets contain air temperature observations at different heights, normally around 2 m above the surface. The exact height depends on snow drift, accumulation, and melting, so the data have been manually checked for data artifacts. Fig. 1 displays the location of the different drifter data in the top panel, while the lower panel indicates for which time period is covered by which in situ type.

Furthermore, 376 buoys from the International Arctic Buoy Programme (IABP) were used for the period between 1 April 2017 and 1 October 2021 to investigate the transition period between the C3S IST CDR and ICDR (International, 2024). The IABP buoys showed larger mean differences and standard deviations (STD) against the C3S IST and other IST datasets, but provide more reference data for longer coherent periods. From the buoy data the air temperature observations were used for validation; it is, however, unknown at which height this temperature was measured.

Furthermore, data from NASA Operation IceBridge (IAKST1B) flights have been used to validate ST in Northern Hemisphere in the period 2012–2019. IceBridge flights have typically been performed between March and May (version 2; Studinger, 2020). During the campaign, a Heitronics KT-19 IR Radiation Pyrometer has been used to obtain IR radiation measurements, which have been converted to surface temperatures assuming an emissivity constant of 0.97. The original IceBridge surface temperatures have a high spatial resolution of about 15 m. This small-scale variability cannot be represented by the coarser resolution of the L3 C3S IST, therefore these temperatures have been averaged for every 25 km.

All validation results are presented in Section 4.

Fig. 1. Location of the drifter in situ data used for the Northern Hemisphere (NH) validation. The lower panel indicates when which drifter data was available between 1982 and 2023. Note that newer in situ data is drawn on top of older observations.

3. Processing methodology and surface temperature algorithms

The flow diagram in Fig. 2 shows the processing chain of the C3S IST data set. The red, blue and purple rectangles on the left side symbolize the data input to the C3S IST processor, while the orange boxes present the calculated parameters in the processor. Finally, the Level 2 (L2) and Level 3 (L3) output productions are depicted on the far right.

Prior to processing the C3S IST data set, SST and IST algorithm coefficients for each applied AVHRR instrument were calculated (listed in Table A.7) for calibration purposes (red part of the flow diagram). Algorithm calibrations are based on Numerical Weather Prediction (NWP) surface temperatures and simulated Top of the atmosphere (TOA) T_B 's, using RTTOV (v 12.3) Radiative Transfer Model (RTM), with atmospheric temperature and humidity from the ERA-Interim reanalysis (Dee et al., 2011).

After algorithm calibrations, the processing of the C3S IST data set is a 3-step procedure: (1) the production of a cloud mask (blue rectangle); (2) computation of surface temperatures, quality levels and uncertainty (orange rectangles); and (3) writing of L2 intermediate output and calculation and writing of the L3 output (right part of Fig. 2). The calibration procedure, the uncertainty algorithms and IST

Quality Levels (QL) are described in detail in Dybkjaer et al., 2018a and presented in Sections 3.2–3.4.

The C3S IST processor consists of a combination of algorithms for sea ice, marginal ice zone (MIZ) and open water, respectively. The IST algorithm is divided into three temperature intervals (cold, middle, and warm) and the SST algorithm is subdivided into three intervals of sun-zenith angle (sza), representing day time, twilight and night time. The MIZ algorithm uses a scaled average of SST and IST. An additional set of algorithms estimate the surface temperature uncertainty and the quality level of the temperature estimate. A similar set of algorithms are also used by the EUMETSAT OSISAF IST processor and described in the OSISAF 205 High Latitude L2 Sea and Sea Ice Surface Temperature Algorithm theoretical basis document (ATBD) (Dybkjaer et al., 2018a).

3.1. Surface temperature algorithms

The selection of a temperature algorithm for a given pixel is a decision tree process. The first decision classifies a pixel into open water or ice surfaces. This distinction is made by a Brightness Temperature (T_B) threshold selection. The surface is sea ice if T_{B11} is colder than 268.95 K and the surface is open water if T_{B11} is warmer than 270.95 K (Dybkjaer et al., 2018a; Vincent et al., 2008). Pixels with intermediate

Fig. 2. Flow diagram of the C3S IST surface temperature processor, including input data (red, blue and purple rectangles), surface temperatures and other parameters (orange boxes) and the 2 output data types in satellite levels 2 and 3 (dark blue rectangles on the right). The red rectangles and dashed box symbolize the input data and a regression calibration procedure used for calibration of each AVHRR instrument.

temperatures are considered to be marginal ice zone pixels, i.e., mixed sea ice and water. This methodology is adapted from the integrated IST/SST algorithm called CASSTA (Vincent et al., 2008).

3.1.1. The IST algorithm

Each ice pixel is subdivided into one of three temperature categories based on T_{B11} temperature thresholds, i.e. cold, medium and warm ice (Key et al., 1997). Each IST temperature domain has individually calibrated algorithm coefficients (provided in Tables A.7 & A.8) fitting the temperature range, i.e., the coefficients $a - d$ in Eq. (1).

$$IST = a + bT_{B11} + c(T_{B11} - T_{B12}) + d(T_{B11} - T_{B12})steta \quad (1)$$

with $steta = \frac{1}{\cos(sza)} - 1$, where sza is the zenith angle of the Sun. $T_{B11} - T_{B12}$ is the average of all cloud-free data points within the closest 3×3 pixels.

The IST temperature domains are the following:

IST_{cold} , cold ice coefficients for $T_{B11} < 240$ K

IST_{medium} , medium ice temperature coefficients for $240 \text{ K} \leq T_{B11} < 260$ K

IST_{warm} , warm ice coefficients for $T_{B11} \geq 260$ K

3.1.2. The SST algorithm

The SST algorithm is represented by a daytime, a nighttime, and a twilight algorithm, each defined by the sun zenith angle, that is, the sza . The three SST algorithms SST_{day} , SST_{night} , and $SST_{twilight}$ are defined in Eqs. (2), (3) and (4), respectively.

SST_{day} (Eq. (2)) is the daytime algorithm for $sza \leq 90$ degrees. The daytime algorithm formalism encompasses a well-documented bias for the North Atlantic area (Le Borgne et al., 2014). Here, T_{clim} is the daily value of the OSTIA SST climatology, used to minimize errors or biases in the absorption term, which is the difference between the temperatures of the 11 and 12 μm channels (Vincent et al., 2008).

SST_{night} (Eq. (3)) is the nighttime algorithm for $sza \geq 110$ degrees. The nighttime algorithm formalism is identical to the operational

nighttime algorithm used in the OSI SAF Global SST product (OSI, 2014).

The twilight algorithm is a scaled temperature of the SST_{day} and SST_{night} algorithms. $SST_{twilight}$ (Eq. (4)) is the algorithm for 110 degree $\geq sza > 90$ degree. $SST_{twilight}$ is scaled linearly between SST_{day} and SST_{night} , as a function of sza .

$$SST_{day} = (a + b \text{ steta})T_{B11} + (c + d \text{ steta} + e T_{clim})(T_{B11} - T_{B12}) + f + g \text{ steta} \quad (2)$$

$$SST_{night} = (a + b \text{ steta})T_{B37} + (c + d \text{ steta})(T_{B11} - T_{B12}) + e + f \text{ steta} \quad (3)$$

$$SST_{twilight} = \frac{SST_{night}(sza - 90) - SST_{day}(sza - 110)}{2} \quad (4)$$

3.1.3. Marginal ice zone algorithm

The marginal ice zone (MIZ) is the region with mixed sea ice and ocean, defined by a temperature range of $268.95 \text{ K} \leq T_{B11} < 270.95$ K (Dybkaer et al., 2018a; Vincent et al., 2008). The marginal ice zone surface temperature (MIZT) algorithm is the scaled average between the IST and SST algorithms (Vincent et al., 2008), as specified in Eq. (5).

$$MIZT = \frac{(T_{B11} - 268.95)SST - (T_{B11} - 270.95)IST}{2} \quad (5)$$

3.2. Tuning methods, NWP coefficients, and atmospheric water vapor correction

Calculations of algorithm coefficients for both IST and SST algorithms are carried out using modeled ERA surface temperatures and simulated Top of the atmosphere (TOA) temperatures. The algorithm coefficients are determined with the individual AVHRR channel response functions and the angular-dependent emissivity. The algorithm coefficients are derived from an Arctic atmospheric profile database that covers 2011 data from the ERA-Interim atmospheric reanalysis data set (Dee et al., 2011).

The initial profile database has 8695 profiles. Profiles selected from a sample of 960 locations each day of the year, at times 0, 6, 12 and 18 UTC. Each profile complies with a land ratio of zero, surface temperatures less than 272 K, a cloud cover of less than 10%, and an ice concentration greater than 90%. Simulated TOA brightness temperatures associated with the ERA-Interim surface temperatures for over 10 different satellite zenith angles (0.0, 36.87, 48.19, 55.15, 60, 63.61, 66.42, 68.68, 70.53, 72.08), were generated using RTTOV12.3 (Hocking, 2014). Ultimately, the simulated IST tuning data set consisted of 86,950 data points.

The snow emissivity, as a function of the incidence angle, was simulated using an implementation of the snow emission model (Dozier and Warren, 1982) with updated ice permittivities (Warren and Brandt, 2008). The spectral response functions for each of the AVHRR instruments were subsequently folded with simulated spectral emissivity.

All algorithm coefficients for the IST and SST algorithms are shown in Tables A.7 and A.8, which are valid for temperatures in Kelvin. IST coefficients refer to Eq. (1) and are divided into warm, medium, and cold conditions, and SST coefficients are divided into daytime and nighttime, Eqs. (2) and (3), respectively.

3.3. Uncertainty algorithm

For each L2 SST or IST retrieval, three independent uncertainties are calculated; a random, a locally systematic and a global systematic uncertainty following the approach used in Bulgin et al. (2016). These uncertainty components represent errors that have distinct correlation properties. The total uncertainty, U_{total} , is the square root of the sum of the three independent squared components (see Eq. (6)).

$$U_{total} = \sqrt{U_{random}^2 + U_{local\ systematic}^2 + U_{global}^2} \quad (6)$$

Each of the three uncertainty components are available in both C3S IST L2 and L3 products. For further details, see Dybkjaer et al. (2018a).

3.4. Quality level decision tree

Quality Levels (QL) are designed to help users filter data. We adopt recommendations from the GHRSSST community that are formalized in the GHRSSST Data Specification (GDS) v2 document (GHRSSST (2012)). For infrared-derived SST (and also IST here, despite it not yet being a GDS standard) six QLs are defined. 0: unprocessed; 1: bad quality/cloudy, 2: worst quality, 3: low quality, 4: acceptable quality, 5: excellent quality. QL assessment is based on the degree of compliance with the quality tests. The degree of compliance is based on the minor and major impact error classes, and the tests are listed in Table 2. The applied tests are selected from empirical validation experience. After testing, a QL is assigned according to the test result as defined in Table 3.

3.5. C3S IST output

The C3S IST data set is produced as Level 3 (L3) with daily mean and min–max temperatures, as well as other parameters such as Quality Levels (QL) and uncertainties. During the processing a Level 2 (L2) swath projection data format is created as well.

3.5.1. Satellite swath projection level 2 data

The C3S IST L2 is produced in the original GAC grid, as the input data described above, i.e. one file per full orbit. Data between latitudes 50° North and 50° South are fill-values.

The L2 data contains the surface temperatures, dates, times, positions and satellite–sun–earth geometry information. Furthermore, a range of additional variables are available in the L2 data files for data filtering purposes. These are:

- Land, ocean and land ice masks

Table 2

Ice surface temperature (IST) and Sea surface temperature (SST) test criteria for pixel-wise quality assessment. A penalty (right column) is given if a pixel does not comply with the test described in the test description (middle column).

Test name	Test description	Penalty for failed test
IST	The IST estimate is within 10 K of the corresponding NWP surface temperature value	Minor
SST	The SST estimate is within 10 K of the corresponding Climate surface temperature from OSTIA	Minor
Sat-Zenith	The scan angle is less than 55 degrees	Minor
Sun-Zenith	The sun elevation is less than 80 degrees	Minor
Cloud Mask	The pixel is cloud free	Major
Cloud Box (3 × 3)	The nearest 9 pixels are cloud free	Minor

Table 3

Description of five Quality Levels (QL), including the number of penalties that a given QL represents (right column).

Quality level	Description	Penalty
QL 0	Missing or erroneous data	
QL 1	Bad Data. Not cloud free according to cloud mask	1 major penalty
QL 2	Worst quality	3-4 minor penalties
QL 3	Low quality	2 minor penalties
QL 4	Acceptable quality	1 minor penalty
QL 5	Best quality	Comply with all tests

- Quality estimates and uncertainties
- Processing flags
- NWP analysis fields of wind speed and air temperature
- Cloud mask
- Daytime probabilities of clouds and ice

The file structure and content of the C3S IST Level 2 (L2) product is similar to the OSISAF L2 IST products (OSI-205), with the spatial resolution being the main difference of the products, i.e. LAC versus GAC formats. A detailed description of the L2 output files is written in the OSI-205 Product User Manual, PUM (Dybkjaer et al., 2018b).

3.5.2. Daily average level 3 grid data

The C3S IST Level 3 (L3) data set is produced to reduce data volume and ease data set handling for applications where very high spatial and temporal resolution is not required, e.g., for most climate analysis. The L2 data are aggregated into daily averages on a fixed 0.25 by 0.25 degrees regular geographical grid. The aggregated files contain daily mean surface temperatures and also 3-hourly binned averages, to relay information on local variability, the daily temperature cycle, and rapid temperature changes.

In the L3 aggregation, all satellite L2 observations with Quality Levels (QL) 4 or 5 were averaged within a given L3 grid cell. To minimize temporal sampling errors and errors due to undetected clouds and other artifacts, each L3 daily mean temperature subsequently must pass a set of tests. Following Nielsen-Englyst et al. (2021), the daily mean IST is discarded if one or more of the following error criteria are met:

- IST exceeds +5 °C, indicating an inconsistency between the ice mask and the surface temperatures.

Table 4

Northern Hemisphere (NH) C3S IST Level 3 (L3) surface temperature comparison with in situ measurements from sea and land ice. The mean difference (MD) is calculated as C3S IST - in situ temperature. STD is the Standard deviation of this difference, RMS is the root mean squared error, Corr the correlation and Nobs is the number of observations. T2m refers to the 2 meter air temperature from in situ observations, IST is the sea ice surface temperature, while LST is the land ice surface temperature.

Type	Parameter	MD	STD	RMS	Corr	Nobs
NP drifting stations (T2m)	IST (°C)	-2.47	2.71	3.67	0.97	4978
ECMWF buoys (T2m)	IST (°C)	-3.39	3.41	4.81	0.95	43014
CRREL drifters (T2m)	IST (°C)	-2.96	3.41	4.52	0.95	16221
SIMB3 drifters (T2m)	IST (°C)	-2.71	2.96	4.01	0.94	4217
IceBridge KT-19 (IST)	IST (°C)	0.20	3.07	3.08	0.94	8982
IceBridge KT-19 (IST)	LST (°C)	-0.56	3.36	3.41	0.93	20084
PROMICE (IST)	LST (°C)	-1.84	3.37	3.95	0.95	37421

Table 5

Southern Hemisphere (SH) C3S IST Level 3 (L3) surface temperature comparison with in situ measurements from sea and land ice. The mean difference (MD) is calculated as C3S IST - in situ temperature. STD is the Standard deviation of this difference, RMS is the root mean squared error, Corr the correlation and Nobs is the number of observations. T2m refers to the 2 meter air temperature from in situ observations, IST is the sea ice surface temperature, while LST is the land ice surface temperature.

Type	Parameter	MD	STD	RMS	Corr	Nobs
ECMWF buoys (T2m)	IST (°C)	-3.63	3.68	5.17	0.83	1033
IceBridge KT-19 (IST)	IST (°C)	-2.96	4.20	5.13	0.40	326
IceBridge KT-19 (IST)	LST (°C)	-4.74	3.25	5.74	0.67	693

- The standard deviation of satellite Level 2 IST during one day exceeds 7.07 °C, corresponding to a sinusoidal daily cycle with a difference between day and night of 20 °C which is considered unrealistic.
- The difference between Level 3 IST and the average of all available 3 h bin averages exceeds 10 °C.
- Level 3 temperature is more than 10 °C colder than the corresponding average of up to 24 neighboring cloud-free observations (in a grid cell square of 5 by 5) with the same surface type

C3S IST L3 data files are produced as one file per hemisphere per day, where each hemisphere is pole-wards from latitudes 50° North and 50° South, respectively. The variables probability-of-cloud, land-and-sea-mask, wind-speed, cloud-mask and processing-flag are not included in the L3 data because they are difficult to aggregate.

4. Validation and stability

In this paper the C3S IST Level 3 (L3) is compared to the in situ data described in Section 2.2, including observations from drifting buoys and NP stations, PROMICE Automatic Weather Stations (AWS) and operation IceBridge flight data. Additional validation results focusing on the Level 2 (L2) C3S IST and its SST component can be found in the product quality assessment report of the data set, which examined its stability over time (Dybkaer et al., 2024).

Tables 4 and 5 show the general validation statistics for the C3S IST L3 and various air temperatures (T2 m) and surface temperature (IST/LST) in situ datasets, for the Northern and Southern Hemisphere, respectively. The validation results are presented separately for the different types of in situ observations, as the instruments have different errors characteristics and are collecting T2 m or IST data. A nearest-neighbor approach was used for all matchups and for IST only grid points with >15% sea ice concentration (SIC) were included. For the C3S IST Level 3 (L3), this method ensures that the in situ observation is

matched only if there is valid data within the C3S IST grid cell covering the in situ location on the same day as the observation. The drifter and weather station data are averaged in daily mean values before matching and validation against the C3S IST L3 daily mean temperatures. Each IceBridge flight is compared with one daily mean C3S IST L3 data file. This can cause discrepancies depending on the representativeness of the IceBridge data for the specific day, as well as the L3 data's representativeness of mean temperature that day, which depends on the quantity and distribution of Level 2 data in a given pixel. During the matchup against each type of in situ data a 3σ filter has been applied to remove outliers, that is, matchups were excluded, when the C3S IST - observation temperature difference is larger than three times the STD of the mean C3S IST - observation difference.

Comparisons between C3S IST and air temperature above snow and ice surfaces have higher mean differences than when C3S IST is compared with reference surface temperature measured by in situ or airborne radiometers (PROMICE and IceBridge data). This is caused by the negative radiation balance on the surface during clear sky conditions in winter darkness (Tonboe et al., 2011).

4.1. Operation IceBridge

Fig. 3(a) shows an example of one IceBridge flight from March 14 2012 that started in northern Greenland and covers the Arctic Ocean, as well as the Beaufort Sea and North Alaska with C3S IST L3 as background. The white patches are areas covered by clouds. The corresponding temperatures along the flight track are shown in Fig. 3(b) for both IceBridge, resampled to 25 km, and the C3S IST L3 surface temperature (25 km). The resampling of the IceBridge data was done by calculating the average temperature for 25 km segments from the flight path. Leads are visible in the high-resolution IceBridge record as spikes, while in the coarser resolution C3S IST L3 the leads are not showing up because of the resolution and the temporal averaging. In addition to these spikes, which have been mostly smoothed out in the resampled IceBridge data shown here, there is otherwise good agreement between the C3S IST L3 and measured surface temperatures with a mean difference of 1.15 °C and STD of 1.64 °C. There is a notable negative temperature spike in the observed IceBridge temperatures around the distance of 250 km, where the C3S IST does not provide a surface temperature. In the C3S IST these data are filtered out due to the presence of clouds, while the very cold observations in the flight data and in the surrounding area in the C3S IST as seen in Fig. 3(a). This indicates either the presence of low clouds below the plane in the observation or falsely classified clouds in the C3S IST.

The overall validation results of all 153 available IceBridge flights in the period 2012–2019 are shown in Tables 4 and 5, here the IceBridge data has been smoothed to 25 km samples, to match the C3S IST resolution and compensate for the aforementioned spikes in the high-resolution observations. For the IST and LST of the Northern Hemisphere (NH) the mean difference is -0.33 °C and standard deviation (STD) 3.30 °C, while for the Southern Hemisphere (SH) the mean difference is -4.17 °C and standard deviation 3.67 °C. The IceBridge observations have mean standard deviations of the 25 km averages of 2.65 °C in the NH and 1.58 °C in the SH, which could explain part of the STD against the C3S IST. The mean STD of the data itself was calculated by first computing the STD for each 25 km segment, corresponding to the C3S IST resolution, and afterwards calculating the average of all these STDs for each hemisphere.

4.2. Land stations

For surface temperature trend analysis it is important that the C3S IST data is temporally consistent, i.e. without biases caused by sensor drift or atmospheric noise. Therefore, Dybkaer et al. (2024) tested the C3S IST data set for temporal consistency against four long in situ temperature time series from AWSs located on the Antarctic ice

Fig. 3. Flight track for operation ice bridge flight number IAKST1B on the 14th March 2012 with (a) C3S IST Level 3 (L3) as background. The start and end of the flight are marked in violet and orange respectively. In figure (b) the operation IceBridge KT-19 radiometer surface temperature is resampled to 25 km resolution in red and the C3S IST L3 surface temperature is shown in blue along the flight track.

Table 6

Statistics for May 2015, MetOp-A satellite, comparing the performance of the implemented CLARA-A2 PPS2014 (V2) and CLARA-A3 PPS2021 (V3) cloud masking. The comparison was done for Northern Hemisphere (NH) sea ice, Greenland land ice and Southern Hemisphere (SH) ice south of 55°S with temperatures below 270 K. ‘ist’ denotes clear sky pixels, while ‘cld’ indicates clouds, the comparison values are in percentage, while the mean difference (MD) and Standard deviation (STD) are in Kelvin (K). Thus ‘istV3 istV2’ denotes the percentage of pixels marked as clear sky in both cloud masking (PPS) versions, while e.g. ‘istV3 cldV2’ describes the percentage of pixels denoted as clear sky in PPS2021 (V3), which are marked as cloudy in PPS2014 (V2).

Area	istV3 istV2	istV3 cldV2	cldV3 istV2	cldV3 cldV2	MD	STD
NH ice	22.58	2.40	3.04	71.98	-0.0010	0.0145
Greenland	61.78	5.05	1.22	31.94	-0.0029	0.0141
SH ice (>55°S & <270K)	36.18	2.46	9.85	51.52	-0.0129	0.0463

sheet and Greenland, covering almost the whole C3S IST period. The difference between C3S IST and the ground observations was shown to not change much throughout the years compared to the overall MD and STDs, which indicates that the C3S IST data is temporally consistent.

For the comparison against PROMICE station data, their calculated surface temperatures are used, which are based on their radiation measurements. For the CDR period until July 2019, 10 stations (“Upper” stations, EGP and CEN) have been used, while for the ICDR period in total 23 stations have been used for the validation against C3S IST L3. Table 4 shows the overall results of the comparison with a mean difference of -1.84 °C and a STD of 3.37 °C. Fig. 4 shows the monthly MD, STD and Number of matchups for the PROMICE validation through time. There is a clear difference between the CDR and ICDR period (blue and red lines), where the stations used for the validation change, resulting in more matchups and a larger MD. The MDs are fairly constant for each period, besides a seasonal pattern, where the values are largest in winter, which might result from the larger variability of temperatures during winter, as well as higher uncertainties related to cloud masking in winter (Nielsen-Englyst et al., 2019).

The shift in the MD between the CDR and ICDR period of approximately 1 °C is unexpected and has been further investigated. We suspect that the bias shift is caused by the different versions of cloud masking software in CLARA-A2/A2.1 and CLARA-A3, PPS2014 and PPS2021, respectively (Karl-Göran et al., 2017; Karlsson et al., 2023). A comparison between PPS2014 and PPS2021 for May 2015 indicates a less strict cloud screening in PPS2021 over the Greenland ice sheet (see Table 6 for statistics of MetOp-A data). Although the specific percentages vary for the different satellites, the trend is the same for all sensors. For MetOp-A 5.05% of the pixels are marked as clear-sky in PPS2021 (V3 in Table 6), while they were indicated as cloudy in

PPS2014 (V2 in Table 6). The opposite, pixels marked as clear sky in PPS2014, while marked as cloudy in PPS2021, is only true for 1.2%. So there is a $\sim 6\%$ difference between the cloud masking. Undetected clouds will statistically lead to a cold bias in the data set, since the cloud tops usually appear colder than the ice/snow surface, which can explain the colder bias in the ICDR over the Greenland ice sheet. Over sea ice the newer PPS2021 is slightly more restrictive than PPS2014, i.e. more pixels are classified as cloudy, thus we do not expect to see the same shift in bias over sea ice.

4.3. Drifting buoys and stations

The larger biases of the C3S IST against drifting NP stations and buoys shown in Tables 4 and 5 result partly from the fact that the drifters provide measured air temperatures (T_2 m), rather than surface temperatures.

Fig. 5 shows the MD, STD and number of matchups of the drifter validation against NP, ECMWF, CRREL and SIMB3 in situ data through time for the Northern Hemisphere. Seasonal patterns are apparent in both MD and STD, where the highest MDs appear in summer and autumn, while the largest STDs occur in autumn and winter. This is in part surprising, given the expected higher variability in temperature during winter and the higher uncertainties in cloud masking in winter, as mentioned before Nielsen-Englyst et al. (2019). The general trend is -0.01 °C/year, while individual MD trends are 0.004 °C/yr for NP, -0.05 °C/yr for ECMWF, -0.01 °C/yr for CRREL and -0.04 °C/yr for SIMB3.

The MD of the SIMB3 drifters in the ICDR period in Fig. 5 and Table 4 align well with the drifter validations of the CDR period, which indicates consistency for the surface area of sea ice, which would fit the

Fig. 4. C3S IST Level 3 (L3) ice land surface temperature (LST) comparison of 2008–2023 to PROMICE station measurements for the Greenland ice sheet. Top panel shows the C3S IST L3 LST - in situ difference, middle panel is showing the Standard deviation (STD) of the difference, bottom panel is showing the number of observations. The data shown here are monthly means.

indications of Table 6, which did not show a large difference in clear sky and cloud-marked pixels over the Northern Hemisphere sea ice.

None of the drifter data used for the validation shown in Fig. 5 does cover both the C3S IST CDR and ICDR. To further investigate possible differences and shifts between the CDR and ICDR period, an additional validation against IABP buoy measurements was made for the 1st of April 2017 to 1 October 2021, two years and three months before and after the CDR/ICDR transition. The daily validation values are depicted in Fig. 6, the black vertical line indicates the shift between CDR and ICDR on the 1st of July 2019. Here, L3 IST is not the complete C3S IST product, but only based on MetOp-A and NOAA-19 data, to make a fairer comparison between the two periods by only using sensors that are present in both periods. The IABP validation MD and STD are significantly larger than for the other drifter validations, partly caused by unavailable quality filtering of the IABP buoys, however, here we are interested in changes over time rather than absolute values. There is no clear shift visible on 1 July 2019 in the IABP validation between the CDR and ICDR period, in contrast to the PROMICE validation. This aligns well with our previous findings that the shift is probably caused by a change in cloud masking processing and only affects the Greenland ice sheet. The mean values of the CDR and ICDR period in Fig. 6 do show a decrease in MD and a slight increase in STD. It is possible that this is the result of the slightly more restrictive cloud masking in the

ICDR, where more pixels are marked as cloudy and thus filtered out. However, there is also an increase in the number of buoys deployed in recent years, especially since the winter of 2019, which might have influenced the MD and STD.

5. IST/LST annual temperature climatology and trends

A yearly mean temperature climatology for sea ice, the Greenland and Antarctic ice sheets is calculated, based on the C3S IST Level 3 (L3) surface temperature data. Separate climatologies are calculated for Northern Hemisphere (NH) sea ice in Section 5.1, Southern Hemisphere (SH) sea ice in Section 5.2, and for Greenland and Antarctic ice sheets in Section 5.3.

The level of trend significance is evaluated based on associated *p*-values, which are the likelihood of the null hypotheses being true, i.e. the likelihood of zero trend in the data set. It is assumed that for *p* values less than 0.05 the null hypothesis is very unlikely and that a positive or negative trend is likely. The figures in this section show only part of the sea ice climatology, which consists of grid points with more than 15% annual mean sea ice fraction during at least 10 years of the C3S IST data record.

Fig. 5. C3S IST Level 3 (L3) Ice surface temperature (IST) comparison 1982–2023 to NP stations, ECMWF, CRREL and SIMB3 buoy measurements for the Northern Hemisphere (NH). Top panel shows the C3S IST L3 IST - in situ difference, middle panel is showing the Standard deviation (STD) of the difference, bottom panel is showing the number of observations. The data shown here are 3-monthly means, indicating seasonal variations.

5.1. Arctic sea ice

The distributed annual NH sea ice surface temperature is shown in Fig. 7. The plots show a general warming of the sea ice surface in the Arctic Ocean, with enhanced warming in and around Barents Sea. This coincides with the investigation of the extent of sea ice, where a comprehensive thinning of sea ice is also observed (Sea Ice Climatology, 2021; Comiso and Hall, 2014). In most of the Arctic Ocean, surface warming between 1 and 1.5 °C/decade is observed, corresponding to a warming of approximately 4 °C for the C3S IST period. The warming of the entire NH sea ice from 1982 to 2023 is calculated to be 4.4 °C, corresponding to a trend of 1.11 °C/decade. This is shown in the annual mean temperature graph in Fig. 7 (bottom left), and is consistent with trends in the ERA interim data record for approximately the same period (Jansen et al., 2020). The annual mean temperature graph also reveals that the warm peaks in September 2007, 2012 and 2020 coincide with the three lowest Arctic sea ice extents (see the extent of sea ice in Sea Ice Climatology, 2021). Another coinciding feature in the temporal evolution of sea ice temperature and sea ice extent (SIE) is that SIE and IST trends have been very small since 2005, indicating a regime change occurred around that time and in particular after the great sea ice loss in 2007 (Sea Ice Extent, 2024).

From the bottom-right panel of Fig. 7 it is evident that p-values in most of the Arctic ocean are well below 0.05, thus rejecting the null-trend hypothesis, i.e. indicating that trends are very reliable. Outside

the Arctic Ocean, the p values are higher, indicating that the null hypothesis cannot be rejected.

5.2. Southern hemisphere sea ice

Temperature trends patterns in the Southern Ocean are different from the trend patterns in the Arctic Ocean. The distributed Southern Ocean temperature trends in the left panel of Fig. 8 show geographically incoherent patches with positive and negative trends. Trends range mainly between 1.0 and -0.5 °C/decade with an average of +0.16 °C/decade, corresponding to a moderate warming of less than 1 °C for sea ice in the southern ocean. This is close to the estimated trend uncertainty of the C3S IST data set (Dybkjaer et al., 2024). The p-test in Fig. 8 also indicates that the null hypothesis cannot be rejected in most areas, since most p-values are greater than 0.1. This indicates that there is no significant positive nor negative surface temperature trend over the SH sea ice, except for two regions of the Davis sea and the Ross to Bellinghausen sea, which show trends of about +0.5 °C/decade (red areas in the right panel of Fig. 8).

5.3. Ice sheets

Distributed temperature trends of the Greenland ice sheet are shown in the top left panel of Fig. 9. In general, the entire ice sheet is warming during the period covered by the C3S IST data set, with the highest

Fig. 6. Level 3 (L3) Ice surface temperature (IST) comparison between 1st of April 2017 and 1st of October 2021 to IABP buoy measurements for the Northern Hemisphere (NH), where the sea ice fraction is larger than 15%. Top panel shows the L3 IST - in situ mean difference (MD), middle panel is showing the Standard deviation (STD) of the difference, bottom panel is showing the number of matchups between buoys and C3S IST L3. The data shown here are daily means, indicating seasonal variations and daily fluctuations. In contrast to the C3S IST product, here the L3 IST is only based on MetOp-A and NOAA-19 data, to ensure a fair comparison between the CDR and ICDR period.

warming closest to the ice edge. The p-test (top right panel) confirms that positive trends are significant, except for areas in the central ice sheet and southern coastal parts, where p-values are higher than 0.1. Here, the null hypothesis cannot be rejected and trends are considered insignificant.

The annual mean temperature trend graph in Fig. 9 shows a positive trend of 0.38 °C/decade, which corresponds to approximately 1.6 °C warming of the Greenland ice sheet from 1982 to 2023. However, the annual mean temperature plot also shows that the Greenland surface temperature increase is not occurring linearly with time, perhaps rather as a step warming in the mid 1990s and the first half of the 2000s.

The temperature trends of the Antarctic ice sheet are much more complex than the trends on the Greenland ice sheet (see left panel of Fig. 10). The major part of the trends of the Antarctic ice sheet trends are considered insignificant, with p values greater than 0.1, as seen in Fig. 10 (right panel). The surface temperature trends are roughly between +1 and -1 °C/decade, with an annual mean trend of -0.13 °C/decade. This is less than the trend uncertainty in the C3S IST data set (Dybkjaer et al., 2024), and the Antarctic ice sheet temperature trends are therefore inconclusive.

6. Discussion

To be able to assess climate trends, it is important that CDRs have a good accuracy and stability, as well as cover a sufficiently long time period (Minnett et al., 2020; GCOS-154, 2011). Ice surface temperature (IST) records are difficult to validate, since good reference data are sparse, as access in Polar Regions is constrained and harsh environmental and dynamical conditions make instrumentation and data collection short-lived and the data quality of the observations cannot always be ensured due, e.g. varying snow cover. To compensate for this, different types of in situ data have been used for the validation of the C3S IST in Section 4. Furthermore, the uncertainty has been

quantified for the daily Surface Temperature (ST) fields, divided into its three components, and the quality levels have been assigned to make data filtering easier.

The C3S IST is an integrated sea and ice surface temperature (SST and IST) data set covering the period 1982 to 2023, which is produced from TIR data from AVHRR 2 & 3 instruments on-board NOAA and MetOp satellites. Hence, all input data are retrieved from identical sensor systems, and subsequent data processing is based on consistent procedures and algorithms. This is the best prerequisite for producing a temporally consistent data set. An analysis of the temporal consistency of the C3S IST data indicates that the C3S IST data record is temporally consistent (Dybkjaer et al., 2024).

In addition to daily mean values, 3-h binned temperatures are also part of the C3S IST Level 3 (L3) data set. The distribution of the data throughout a day is not always uniform, due to e.g. cloud cover. In case the satellite data do not accurately represent the true daily mean, the satellite value will be randomly biased warm or cold. However, errors are expected to be larger for the L3 than for the L2 data, due to re-sampling of both C3S IST L2 data and in situ measurements.

Overall, the validation results in Section 4 show consistent results. Despite that the PROMICE Upper AWSs are located in a part of the ice sheet with small slopes (<1°) in the upper ablation zone of the Greenland ice sheet, and that the in situ temperatures are estimated surface temperatures, this data set is not the ideal reference for the L3 product. The large grid size of the L3 product will occasionally overlap the lower ice sheet slope, where temperatures, atmospheric conditions, and emissivity can differ largely from the conditions at the upper AWS location. Therefore, the values in Table 4 are likely to be overestimated. For PROMICE the MD was -1.84 °C with an STD of 3.37 °C, while for drifters the MD ranged from -2.46 to -3.38 °C with STDs of 2.69 to 3.40 °C, for the Northern Hemisphere. Interestingly, the MDs and STDs of the drifters seem more consistent than the two PROMICE validation periods. Since such a contrast is not visible in the drifter validations, it

Fig. 7. Northern Hemisphere sea ice climatology from 1982 to 2023, based on C3S IST Level 3 (L3) data. Temperature climatology (top left), temperature trends (top right), reliability of linear trend estimates (p-values, bottom right) and annual mean sea ice temperature with linear regression line (temperature trend, bottom left).

Fig. 8. Southern Hemisphere sea ice annual mean temperature trend for 1982 to 2023 (left panel), based on C3S IST Level 3 (L3) data. Reliability of the linear trend estimates (p-values) is depicted in the panel on the right.

Fig. 9. Greenland ice sheet annual mean temperature trends based on C3S IST Level 3 (L3) data. Temperature trends (top left), reliability of linear trend estimates (p-values, top right) and annual mean ice sheet temperature with linear regression line (temperature trend, bottom) are shown.

is unclear how much of the differences is caused by the change between the CDR and ICDR, and how much is caused by the change of PROMICE stations used for the validation.

After investigating the MD shift in the PROMICE validation, we suspect that the change of the cloud masking software between CLARA-A2/A2.1 and CLARA-A3, PPS2014 and PPS2021 respectively, could have affected the data set, as indicated by the increase of clear sky pixels in Table 6, which might have introduced the cold bias in the ICDR. The differences between PPS2014 and PPS2021 indicated in the Table 6, match the Greenland ice sheet and sea ice drifter validation results. No MD shift was observed in the drifter validation, which fits the statistics, that PPS2021 is only slightly more restrictive than PPS2014, i.e. it classifies more pixels as cloudy, over sea ice. An additional IABP drifter validation was performed from 1 April 2017 to 1 October 2021 covering the CDR to ICDR transition was performed against a L3 IST solely based on MetOp-A and NOAA-19 to further investigate the data for possible inconsistencies. The validation results shown in Fig. 6 did not show a clear shift between the two periods. Thus, the MD shift between the CDR and ICDR only seems to be present

over the Greenland ice sheet. This issue will be further investigated when a more reliable in situ data set has been compiled, which covers both the CDR and ICDR period.

The IceBridge high STD might be partly due to the lack of cloud masking of the flight data, where instead of the surface, the cloud tops were measured, which are much colder. The data might also experience a clear sky bias, where observations without clouds present are colder than with cloud cover. However, these high-resolution flight observations show the closest alignment with the C3S IST in the Northern Hemisphere, with a bias of only 0.20 °C and STD of 3.07 °C for IST and a bias of -0.56 °C and STD of 3.36 °C for LST. This is expected since the drifting buoys, for example ECMWF and CRREL, cannot ensure a constant height at which the air temperature is measured. Comparisons for the Southern Hemisphere showed larger biases and STDs than for the Northern Hemisphere in general, with biases between -2.96 and -4.74 °C and STDs ranging from 3.25 to 4.20 °C. The validation results against the ECMWF buoys indicate equally good IST performance in both hemispheres and STD over land ice compared to IceBridge data are also similar, while the MD is larger in the Southern Hemisphere. The

Fig. 10. Antarctica ice sheet annual mean temperature trend for 1982 to 2023 (left panel), based on C3S IST Level 3 (L3) data. Reliability of the linear trend estimates (p-values) is depicted in the panel on the right.

Table A.7

Coefficients for ice surface temperature (IST) (Eq. (1)) for all applied satellites for the three temperature domains; cold, medium and warm.

sat id	alg. \coeff.	a	b	c	d	e	f	g
NOAA 7	IST_{cold}	-3.152	1.013	0.936	0.025	-	-	-
	IST_{medium}	-3.383	1.014	1.528	0.012	-	-	-
	IST_{warm}	-3.629	1.014	1.498	0.329	-	-	-
NOAA 9	IST_{cold}	-2.894	1.012	0.736	0.034	-	-	-
	IST_{medium}	-3.969	1.016	1.601	-0.073	-	-	-
	IST_{warm}	-4.959	1.019	1.679	0.288	-	-	-
NOAA 11	IST_{cold}	-2.945	1.013	0.805	0.029	-	-	-
	IST_{medium}	-3.530	1.014	1.553	-0.043	-	-	-
	IST_{warm}	-4.373	1.017	1.603	0.284	-	-	-
NOAA 12	IST_{cold}	-3.810	1.016	1.086	0.056	-	-	-
	IST_{medium}	-2.453	1.010	1.320	0.159	-	-	-
	IST_{warm}	-2.860	1.012	1.397	0.376	-	-	-
NOAA 14	IST_{cold}	-3.458	1.015	0.933	0.002	-	-	-
	IST_{medium}	-3.196	1.013	1.273	0.056	-	-	-
	IST_{warm}	-3.145	1.013	1.247	0.319	-	-	-
NOAA 15	IST_{cold}	-3.562	1.015	1.079	0.056	-	-	-
	IST_{medium}	-3.476	1.014	1.560	0.099	-	-	-
	IST_{warm}	-3.617	1.015	1.481	0.403	-	-	-
NOAA 16	IST_{cold}	-3.537	1.015	1.213	0.063	-	-	-
	IST_{medium}	-1.643	1.007	1.144	0.222	-	-	-
	IST_{warm}	-1.125	1.005	1.333	0.343	-	-	-
NOAA 17	IST_{cold}	-3.173	1.014	0.843	0.032	-	-	-
	IST_{medium}	-3.410	1.014	1.468	0.002	-	-	-
	IST_{warm}	-4.084	1.016	1.482	0.309	-	-	-
NOAA 18	IST_{cold}	-3.046	1.013	0.852	-0.002	-	-	-
	IST_{medium}	-2.465	1.010	1.160	0.035	-	-	-
	IST_{warm}	-2.270	1.009	1.245	0.227	-	-	-
NOAA 19	IST_{cold}	-3.245	1.014	0.937	0.003	-	-	-
	IST_{medium}	-2.083	1.009	1.007	0.110	-	-	-
	IST_{warm}	-1.137	1.005	1.106	0.253	-	-	-
METOP C	IST_{cold}	-2.650	1.011	0.931	-0.084	-	-	-
	IST_{medium}	-0.420	1.002	1.042	-0.014	-	-	-
	IST_{warm}	0.489	0.998	-1.107	0.092	-	-	-
METOP B	IST_{cold}	-3.216	1.014	0.866	0.036	-	-	-
	IST_{medium}	-3.200	1.013	1.443	0.024	-	-	-
	IST_{warm}	-3.877	1.015	1.461	0.311	-	-	-
METOP A	IST_{cold}	-3.216	1.014	0.866	0.036	-	-	-
	IST_{medium}	-3.200	1.013	1.443	0.024	-	-	-
	IST_{warm}	-3.877	1.015	1.461	0.311	-	-	-

validation results for Southern Hemisphere are considered less reliable due to the small volume of in situ observations. The comparison in Fig. 5 does not show a large trend of biases between C3S IST and the observations in situ Dybkjaer et al., 2024 and the comparison shown in Fig. 5, indicating that the data record is stable.

Climatologies were calculated for the sea ice areas in the Northern and Southern Hemispheres and for the Greenland and Antarctic ice sheets in Section 5. The distributed temperature trend analysis shows warming of the Arctic sea ice and for the Greenland ice sheet. Most of the Arctic sea ice has warmed more than 4 °C during the time covered by the data set, with an annual trend of 0.11 °C/year. Furthermore, for the period before 2016, the two warmest years of the arctic sea ice coincide with the two lowest sea ice extents, 2007 and 2012 (Sea Ice Climatology, 2021). The Greenland ice sheet shows a mean warming trend of 0.04 °C/year, with higher values near the ice sheet margin. No clear warming of the Southern Ocean sea ice has been observed. Likewise, the Antarctic ice sheet does not show significant evidence of warming during the period 1982 and 2023, except an area in eastern Antarctica, which shows a significant trend of -0.5 °C/decade.

7. Conclusion

This paper presented the C3S IST L3 data set, produced from AVHRR GAC data. The data set is available as daily NetCDF files in a 0.25° latitude–longitude grid per hemisphere. The daily files include daily mean temperatures and 3 hourly mean temperatures to preserve daily variability and a range of other variables, which are useful for data filtering and post-processing, such as data quality levels and uncertainty estimates. The C3S IST currently covers the period 1982 to 2023, presenting a long and consistent data set, usable for trend analysis and input to reanalysis or other surface temperature products.

A validation against different in situ sources was presented in Section 4. Comparisons against surface temperature measurements showed better results than against air temperature observations, by 1–3 °C differences. Especially the high-resolution observations of the IceBridge flights and the PROMICE station data demonstrated smaller biases of 0.20 °C to -1.84 °C in the Northern Hemisphere. The validation results throughout the record showed consistent mean differences compared to the drifting buoy and station data, while a change between the CDR and ICDR period was found in the PROMICE validation for the Greenland ice sheet, which might be explained by the change in the cloud masking software version. This issue will be further investigated with more in situ data sets and cloud masking tests.

Table A.8
Coefficients for sea surface temperature (SST) (Eq. (2) and (3)) for all applied satellites for the two sun elevation domains; day and night time.

sat id	alg. \coeff.	a	b	c	d	e	f	g
NOAA 7	SST_{day}	1.023	0.009	-1.135	0.296	0.010	-6.016	-1.448
	SST_{night}	1.017	0.030	1.249	0.084	-3.893	-7.216	-
NOAA 9	SST_{day}	1.026	0.013	-0.603	0.283	0.008	-6.739	-2.495
	SST_{night}	1.019	0.032	1.407	0.054	-4.242	-7.687	-
NOAA 11	SST_{day}	1.024	0.011	-1.017	0.278	0.010	-6.452	-2.069
	SST_{night}	1.019	0.031	1.311	0.064	-4.253	-7.520	-
NOAA 12	SST_{day}	1.021	0.008	-1.442	0.304	0.011	-5.630	-1.223
	SST_{night}	1.016	0.030	1.149	0.115	-3.477	-7.046	-
NOAA 14	SST_{day}	1.023	0.007	-1.151	0.292	0.009	-6.225	-0.737
	SST_{night}	1.016	0.029	1.051	0.107	-3.654	-6.836	-
NOAA 15	SST_{day}	1.023	0.010	-1.214	0.278	0.010	-6.230	-1.717
	SST_{night}	1.019	0.029	1.203	0.076	-4.419	-6.955	-
NOAA 16	SST_{day}	1.016	0.000	-1.960	0.350	0.012	-4.451	0.917
	SST_{night}	1.015	0.024	1.049	0.140	-3.645	-5.585	-
NOAA 17	SST_{day}	1.024	0.010	-1.070	0.278	0.009	-6.354	-1.737
	SST_{night}	1.018	0.031	1.221	0.076	-4.089	-7.314	-
NOAA 18	SST_{day}	1.020	0.002	-1.531	0.304	0.010	-5.350	0.432
	SST_{night}	1.016	0.027	0.990	0.119	-3.559	-6.238	-
NOAA 19	SST_{day}	1.018	-0.002	-1.699	0.322	0.010	-4.809	1.612
	SST_{night}	1.015	0.024	0.906	0.137	-3.374	-5.510	-
METOP C	SST_{day}	0.973	-0.001	-10.517	0.422	0.040	8.176	0.955
	SST_{night}	1.006	0.018	0.619	0.271	-0.498	-3.769	-
METOP B	SST_{day}	1.030	0.017	-0.300	0.255	0.006	-8.132	-3.737
	SST_{night}	1.019	0.036	1.200	0.058	-4.453	-8.877	-
METOP A	SST_{day}	1.030	0.017	-0.300	0.255	0.006	-8.132	-3.737
	SST_{night}	1.019	0.036	1.200	0.058	-4.453	-8.877	-

Trends were calculated for IST and ice LST in both hemispheres. Especially in the Northern Hemisphere significant trends have been located, exceeding +4° throughout the data record (+1 °C/decade) for IST and +2 ° along the coast of Greenland. In the Southern Hemisphere the trends have been less significant, besides a -0.5 °C/decade trend in central, high altitude part of eastern Antarctica, and +0.5 °C/decade around west Antarctica, between the Ross and Amundsen seas.

A C3S IST version (v2) is planned for release in 2025, which will extend the current data set to the present day and improve consistency.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Wiebke Margitta Kolbe: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Investigation. **Gorm Dybkjær:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Rasmus T. Tonboe:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Steinar Eastwood:** Writing – original draft, Software, Investigation. **Pia Nielsen-Englyst:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation. **Jacob Høyer:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology. **André Toft Jensen:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Software. **Magnus Barfod Suhr:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Software.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix

See Tables A.7 and A.8.

Data availability

A dedicated product page for the C3S IST in the Climate Data Store (CDS) will launch soon. The data and continuous monthly updates of the C3S IST are already available with approximately 2 weeks latency. Retrieval software such as ‘wget’ can be used to download daily files for each hemisphere [nh/sh] from http links of the following format where [yyyymmdd] denotes the date as year, month & day:

For the CDR:

[http://cataloguedata-ecv.data.compute.cci1.ecmwf.int/data5/si-temperature/data/cdr_ice_ist_v1p0/\[yyyy\]/\[mm\]/\[yyyymmdd\]000000-DM I_MET-L3S_GHRSSST-STskin-AVHRR_\[nh/sh\]_SST_IST-CDR-v1.0-fv1.0.nc](http://cataloguedata-ecv.data.compute.cci1.ecmwf.int/data5/si-temperature/data/cdr_ice_ist_v1p0/[yyyy]/[mm]/[yyyymmdd]000000-DM I_MET-L3S_GHRSSST-STskin-AVHRR_[nh/sh]_SST_IST-CDR-v1.0-fv1.0.nc)

For the ICDR:

[http://cataloguedata-ecv.data.compute.cci1.ecmwf.int/data5/si-temperature/data/icdr_ice_ist_v1p1/\[yyyy\]/\[mm\]/\[yyyymmdd\]000000-DM I_MET-L3S_GHRSSST-STskin-AVHRR_\[nh/sh\]_SST_IST-ICDR-v1.1-fv1.0.nc](http://cataloguedata-ecv.data.compute.cci1.ecmwf.int/data5/si-temperature/data/icdr_ice_ist_v1p1/[yyyy]/[mm]/[yyyymmdd]000000-DM I_MET-L3S_GHRSSST-STskin-AVHRR_[nh/sh]_SST_IST-ICDR-v1.1-fv1.0.nc)

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